

SITUATIONAL UNDERSTANDING CAPACITY, ENGLISH LEARNING ATTITUDE, AND RESEARCH INTEREST OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS: A MODERATION ANALYSIS

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Abstract. The current study was set evaluate whether situational understanding capability have significant moderating effect on the interaction between English learning attitude and research interest of senior high school students. In this study, the researcher selected the 202 senior high school students in Tugbok District in Davao City as the respondents of the study. Stratified random sampling technique was utilized in the selection of the respondents. Non-experimental quantitative research design using descriptive-correlational method was employed. The data collected were subjected on the following statistical tools: Mean, Partial Correlation, and Regression Analysis. Descriptive analysis showed that English learning attitude and situational understanding capability were described as extensive, while, research interest of senior high school students was rated as moderately extensive. Further, partial correlation analysis demonstrated that there is significant relationship between English learning attitude and research interest of senior high school students when moderated by situational understanding capability. Evidently, regression analysis proved that situational understanding capability have significant moderating effect on the interaction between English learning attitude and research interest of senior high school students. In other words, situational understanding capability is a significant moderator on the interaction between English learning attitude and research interest of senior high school students. The study, therefore, conducted for further utilization of findings through publication in reputable research journal.

KEY WORDS

1. Teaching English.
2. English learning attitude.
3. research interest.

1. Introduction

The lack of interest in research activities among students can have several impacts on teaching practices. Research activities are crucial for developing critical thinking and analytical skills. A lack of interest may result in students not fully participating in these activities, hindering the development of important cognitive abilities that are essential for effective teaching practices. Lack of interest in research may result in limited engagement in inquiry-based learning. Research activities often involve exploring questions, conducting investigations, and finding solutions. When students lack interest, the effectiveness of inquiry-based

teaching practices may be compromised. Addressing the lack of interest in research activities may involve incorporating more engaging and relevant research topics, providing support and guidance, and demonstrating the real-world applications of research in students' lives. It requires a strategic and motivational approach to make research activities more appealing and meaningful to students, enhancing the overall effectiveness of teaching practices. Previous researches indicated that the diminishing interest towards research studies among students in higher education remains an increasing problem among educators and policy makers worldwide. For instance, Khan et al. (2018) reported that a lack of interest in such studies can result in slower advancements in science, technology, medicine, and other critical areas, potentially hindering societal development since investigative studies are at the forefront of driving innovation and progress in various fields. In same vein, Garrett and Cutting (2019) reported that lack of interest in research may result in reduced participation in extracurricular academic opportunities, such as research competitions or conferences. This limits students' exposure to additional learning experiences beyond the regular classroom setting. Likewise, Pliske et al. (2015) confirmed that a lack of interest may lead to superficial or incomplete research, affecting the overall quality of student work and limiting the effectiveness of assessment-based teaching practices. As pointed out by Borja (2016), a positive attitude towards learning English can enhance students' motivation to engage with the language. When students believe that learning English is enjoyable and valuable, they are more likely to put in the effort required to improve their language skills. According to Gallagher (2015), an optimistic attitude can lead to more effective learning. When students approach English learning with a positive mindset, they are more open to trying new strategies, seeking help when needed, and actively participating in language-related activities. Getie and Popescu (2019) mentioned that when students enjoy the process of learning English, it becomes more than just a task; it becomes a pleasurable experience. As defined by Schraw and Dennison (1994), situational understanding capability is the students' ability to perceive, comprehend, and navigate various educational contexts, challenges, and situations effectively. According to Amolloh et al. (2018), situational understanding fosters critical thinking skills, enabling students to analyze information, evaluate options, and make well-informed decisions. Situational understanding requires application of critical thinking that demonstrate deeper mastery of what to teach and how to teach requiring concrete experiences, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization and active experimentation. Likewise, Antovska and Kostov (2016) found that students who understand the relevance and context of their studies are more likely to stay engaged and motivated in their learning. Meanwhile, Meşe (2021) pointed out that when students are interested in research studies, they are more likely to actively participate in class, complete assignments with enthusiasm, and seek out additional resources for self-directed learning. The author also noted that developing a passion for research work can instill a life-long love of learning and the habit of seeking knowledge, which is valuable beyond formal education. Adding more, Flowerday and Shell (2015) affirmed that research works encourage students to think critically, analyze information, and evaluate evidence. These skills are applicable to decision-making in both personal and professional life, helping individuals make informed choices. Likewise, Shaukat et al. (2016) viewed that proficiency in research tasks is beneficial not only in academic and professional settings but also in making well-informed personal decisions. Several studies indicated that there is a link between access to resources and interest in investigative studies among stu-

dents. Hourigan et al. (2016) found that proficiency in English is often a valuable asset in research-related careers and academia. Students with strong English language skills are better positioned to pursue research opportunities, publish their work, and advance in their chosen fields. Adding more, O'Keefe et al. (2017) concluded a positive English learning attitude can motivate students to participate in international research collaborations, conferences, and exchange programs. Engaging with scholars and researchers from different countries can stimulate their interest in research and expose them to a global academic community. In addition, Awan and Ullah (2011) showed that a positive English learning attitude enables students to tap into a vast pool of international research and scholarly work. Despite the growing body of literature examining the relationship between English learning attitude and research interest among students, there is a noticeable research gap pertaining to the role of situational understanding capability as a moderator in this relationship among senior high school students. While there have been studies exploring these

variables separately, there is a dearth of research that specifically investigates how situational understanding capability influences the strength and nature of the relationship between English learning attitude and research interest in this particular educational context. Thus, it is in this context that the researcher felt the need to fill-in the research gap of conducting a study in the Philippine setting, particularly in Tugbok District in Davao City using a quantitative approach. Specifically, the researcher used descriptive-correlational design to have a better understanding on the moderating effect of situational understanding capability on the interaction between English learning attitude and research interest of senior high school students. The present study intends to contribute to the limited body of knowledge regarding the research interest of senior high school students in the context of students in Davao City. This could provide insights into the contingencies and boundary conditions of relationships, helping researchers develop more precise theoretical frameworks.

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis. In the preparation of this paper, the researcher employed artificial intelligence tools for proofreading. Specifically, AI was utilized to enhance the accuracy, coherence, and overall quality of the manuscript. This practice is being explicitly stated to maintain transparency and adhere to ethical standards in research. The usage of AI for proofreading reflects a commitment to leveraging advanced technologies responsibly and acknowledges the increasing prevalence and capability of AI in academic and professional writing.

2.1. Research Design—In this study, the researcher utilized quantitative descriptive-correlational technique of research to gather data ideas, facts and information related to the study. Bhandari (2020) described quantitative research is a research strategy that focuses on quantifying the collection and analysis of data. It is formed from a deductive approach where

emphasis is placed on the testing of theory, shaped by empiricist and positivist philosophies, while, non-experimental research is a research that lacks the manipulation of an independent variable. Rather than manipulating an independent variable, researchers conducting non-experimental research simply measure variables as they naturally occur in real world. Mean-

while, descriptive correlational research according to Creswell (2013) is a study in which the researcher is primarily interested in describing relationships among variables, without seeking to establish a causal connection. In this study the researcher was able to look into the English learning attitude, research interest, and situational understanding capability of senior high school students. Specifically, the study investigated the relationships among variables for the purpose of determining the moderating effect of situation understanding capability on the interaction between English learning attitude and research interests of senior high school students. In this study, the used of hierarchical regression analysis would be appropriate because the researchers can develop more accurate and context-specific predictive models. Instead of assuming a constant relationship between variables, they can account for variations that occur based on the moderating variable's influence.

2.2. Research Respondents—The respondents of the study were the Grade 12 students in Tugbok District in Division of Davao City. In this study, the 202 respondents was selected through stratified random sampling technique. Stratified random sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. According to Shi (2015), in stratified random sampling, or stratification, the strata are formed based on members' shared attributes or characteristics such as income or educational attainment Stratified random sampling is appropriate in this study because there is heterogeneity in a population that can be classified with ancil-

The second part of the instrument was about the research interest of senior high school students which was intellectualized by Hussain et al. (2016), and divided among four domains namely: positive learning environment; technological proficiency; perceived competence; and

lary information. In this study, certain inclusion criteria were implemented in determining the respondents of the study. The primary consideration of this study is to select respondents who can provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. The inclusion criteria are as follows: students enrolled in senior high school (grades 11 and 12); students with varying levels of English proficiency to capture a diverse range of attitudes and understanding; students who are available during the data collection period, considering class schedules and other commitments; and who voluntarily signed the ICF were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was limited to the nature of the problem based on the research questions and, thus, did not consider the gender and socio-economic status of the students.

2.3. Research Instrument—The study employed the questionnaires adapted from different studies and were modified to fit the context of the respondents of this study. The instrument was divided into two parts. The first part of the instrument was about English learning attitude of students. This questionnaire was adapted from the study of Crivilare (2019) which is measured in terms of behavior towards learning, understanding of concepts, and feelings towards learning. The reliability of the new scale obtained a Chronbach's alpha value of 0.916. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the respondents made use the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of English learning attitude of senior high school students, the researcher made use the range of means, description and interpretation as presented below:

reinforcement. The reliability of the new scale obtained a Chronbach's alpha value of 0.920. The researcher modified the questionnaire by grouping all the items each dimension under each domain. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the items the respondents made

English Learning Attitude of Senior High School Students

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The English learning attitude of senior high school students is always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The English learning attitude of senior high school students is oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The English learning attitude of senior high school students is sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The English learning attitude of senior high school students is seldom observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The English learning attitude of senior high school students is never observed.

use the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of research interest of senior high school students, the researcher made use of the

Research Interest of Senior High School Students

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The research interest of senior high school students is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The research interest of senior high school students is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The research interest of senior high school students is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The research interest of senior high school students is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The research interest of senior high school students is never manifested.

The third part of the instrument concerned about the situational understanding capability of senior high school students. This questionnaire was adapted from Schraw and Dennison (1994). The reliability of the original scale obtained a Chronbach’s alpha value of 0.914. In the man-

ner of answering the questionnaire, the respondents made use the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of situational understanding capability of senior high school students, the researcher made use the range of means, description and interpretation as presented below:

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—Steps were undergone by the researcher in conducting the study after the validation of the research questionnaire. Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher secured the permission to conduct the study. The researcher secured the

endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in College where the researcher is studying, Inc., Davao City. The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in College where the researcher is studying, Inc., Davao City was attached to the permission let-

Situational Understanding Capability of Senior High School Students

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The situational understanding capability of senior high school students is always evident.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The situational understanding capability of senior high school students is oftentimes evident.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The situational understanding capability of senior high school students is sometimes evident.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The situational understanding capability of senior high school students is seldom evident.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The situational understanding capability of senior high school students is never evident.

ters to be endorsed to the schools division superintendent, and then to the school principals of the secondary public schools in Tugbok District, Davao City. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. The researcher proceeded to the distribution of the research instrument to the respondents after the approval to conduct the study. Upon the distribution of the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey was briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. For the administration of the

questionnaire, the study was done in the second quarter of school year 2023-2024. More so, the respondents of the study were given enough testing time for the questionnaires to be finished. After which, the collected data were subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After the data retrieval of the questionnaire, the scores of each respondents was tallied to organized the data per indicator. After which, each score were subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing the English learning attitude, research interest, and situational understanding capability of senior high school students in Tugbok District, Davao City. This was use to supply the answer for objectives 1 and 2. Partial Correlation. It was used in this study to asses the relationship between English learning attitude and research interest of senior

high school students in Tugbok District, Davao City when moderated by situational understanding capability. It is a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. In a sample it is usually denoted by *r*. Regression Analysis. It was applied to evaluate the moderating effect of situational understanding capability on the interaction between English learning attitude and research interest of senior high school students in Tugbok District, Davao City.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the objectives of the study as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extents of English learning attitude, research interest, and situational understanding capability of senior high school students; the significant relationship between English learning attitude and research interest of

senior high school students when moderated by situational understanding capability; and the moderating effect of situational understanding capability on the interaction between English learning attitude and research interest of senior high school students.

Table 1 shows the summary on English learning attitude of senior high school students in Tugbok District, Davao City. It shows that the overall mean of English learning attitude of senior high school students is 3.48 which is described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed. More so, English learning attitude of senior high school students in terms of behavior towards learning acquired the highest mean score of 3.53 described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed, while, English learning attitude of senior high school students in terms of feelings towards learning got the lowest mean score of 3.42 described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed by the senior high school students.

Table 1. Summary on English Learning Attitude of Senior High School Students in Tugbok District, Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Behavior Towards Learning	3.53	Extensive
Understanding of Concepts	3.50	Extensive
Feelings Towards Learning	3.42	Extensive
Overall	3.48	Extensive

As shown in the Table 2 is the summary of research interest of senior high school students. As shown in the table, pedagogical accomplishment of teachers obtained an overall mean score of 3.32 with a descriptive rating of moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested by the students. Adding more, results on Table 9 show that research interest of senior high school students in terms of technology proficiency acquired the highest mean score of 3.44 described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested, while, research interest of senior high school students in terms of perceived competence acquire the lowest mean score of 3.24 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested by the senior high school students.

Table 2. Summary on Research Interest of Senior High School Students

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Positive Learning Environment	3.27	Moderately Extensive
Technological Proficiency	3.44	Extensive
Perceived Competence	3.24	Moderately Extensive
Reinforcement	3.28	Moderately Extensive
Overall	3.31	Moderately Extensive

The result implies that the attraction or enthusiasm for activities, courses, or careers that involve the systematic and in-depth exploration, analysis, and research of various subjects, issues, or phenomena is sometimes manifested. This is congruent to Hussain’s et al. (2011) idea that interest in investigative studies reflects a genuine curiosity and motivation to uncover information, solve problems, and gain a deeper understanding of the world through investiga-

tive methods. Students with a strong interest in investigative studies often actively engage in research, critical thinking, and problem-solving activities related to their chosen fields. Meşe (2021) asserted that when students are interested in investigative studies, they are more likely to actively participate in class, complete assignments with enthusiasm, and seek out additional resources for self-directed learning.

Situational Understanding Capability Situational understanding capability of senior high school students as shown in Table 3 has a category mean of 3.47 described as extensive and interpreted that this domain of research interest of senior high school students is oftentimes evident. Adding on, the mean ratings of the different items range from 3.22 to 3.86. Specif-

ically, the item Knowing when each strategy I use will be most effective has a mean rating of 3.22 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as item sometimes evident. The item Using my intellectual strengths to compensate for my weaknesses reflects a mean rating of 3.87 described as extensive and interpreted as item oftentimes evident.

Table 3. Situational Understanding Capability of Senior High School Students

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Learning best when I know something about the topic	3.57	Extensive
Using different learning strategies depending on the situation	3.23	Moderately Extensive
Using my intellectual strengths to compensate for my weaknesses	3.86	Extensive
Knowing when each strategy I use will be most effective	3.22	Moderately Extensive
Mean	3.47	Extensive

This means that students’ ability to perceive, comprehend, and navigate various educational contexts, challenges, and situations effectively is oftentimes evident. The result supports the findings of Sugiharto et al. (2018) that situational understanding necessitates the use of critical thinking and problem-solving abilities that exhibit a deeper command of declarative and procedural information. This calls for experience learning as well, ideally through partici-

pation in professional communities of practice. Also, the result agrees with the idea of Kiesewetter et al. (2016) that situational understanding equips students with problem-solving skills that are essential for tackling academic challenges and real-world issues.

Relationship Between English Learning Attitude and Research Interest of Senior High School Students when Moderated by Situational Understanding Capability

The results on the analysis on the relationship between English learning attitude and research interest of senior high school students when Moderated by situational understanding capability are presented. Partial Correlation was utilized to determine the relationship between the variables mentioned. Table 4 shows that English learning attitude has a significant positive relationship with the research interest of senior high school students when moderated by situational understanding capability with a p-value

of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .556, p < 0.05$). It means that as the extent of English learning attitude changes, research interest of senior high school students also significantly changes when moderated by situational understanding capability. This leads to the rejection of null hypothesis of no significant relationship between English learning attitude and research interests of senior high school students when moderated by situational understanding capability.

Table 4. Relationship Between English Learning Attitude and Research Interest of Senior High School Students when Moderated by Situational Understanding Capability

Variables	Research Interest	Situational Understanding Capability (Moderator)	
Behavior Towards Learning	0.843*	0.000	Reject H0
Understanding of Concepts	0.552*	0.000	Reject H0
Feelings Towards Learning	0.771*	0.000	Reject H0
Overall English Learning Attitude	0.556*	0.000	Reject H0

*Significant @ $p < 0.05$

The result corroborates with Hourigan’s et al. (2016) idea that situational understanding often requires critical thinking skills. Improving critical thinking can, in turn, enhance the ability to analyze and interpret information in both English learning and research activities. Students with well-developed critical thinking skills may approach English learning and research with a more positive and open mindset. According to Mata et al. (2012), English becomes a medium through which students can communicate and share their research findings with a broader audience, fostering a deeper connection between their research interests and language learning. As students develop research interests, the ability to understand and navigate various situations can help them apply their research in real-world contexts.

Moderating Effect of Situational Understanding Capability on the Interaction Between English Learning Attitude and Research Interest

of Senior High School Students

The moderating effect of situational understanding capability (SUC) on the Interaction Between English learning attitude (ELA) and research interest (RI) of senior high school students were tested using regression analysis. Results on the Table 13 shows that the Beta coefficients for the Step 1 analysis of English learning attitude (ELA) and research interest (RI) were = 0.112, S.E. = 0.055, $p < 0.05$; and Situational Understanding Capacity (SUC) and research interest (RI) were = 0.209, S.E.=0.051, $p < 0.05$. When English learning attitude (ELA) and situational understanding capability (SUC) were included as the only independent variables (without including an interaction term), the regression model explained 44.40%. Moreover, Beta coefficients for the Step 2 analysis of English learning attitude (ELA) and research interest (RI) of senior high school students were = 0.380, S.E. = .040, $p < 0.05$; situational understanding

capability (SUC) and research interest (RI) of senior high school students were $\beta = 0.180$, S.E. = 0.044, $p < 0.05$; and moderator (ELA*SUC) and research interest (RI) of senior high school students were $\beta = 0.231$, S.E. = 0.056, $p < 0.05$. Also, it was indicated that when an interaction between English learning attitude (ELA) and situational understanding capability (SUC) was added, the percentage of variance in research interest (RI) of senior high school students was 67.90

Table 5. Moderating Effect of Situational Understanding Capability on the Interaction Between English Learning Attitude and Research Interest of Senior High School Students

Step 1	B	Beta	S.E	p-value	Decision
English Language Attitude (ELA)	.112**	.132	.055	.000	Reject H0
Situational Understanding Capacity (SUC)	.209**	.077	.051	.000	Reject H0
$R^2 = 0.444$	F-value = 103.564**			p-value = 0.000	
Step 2					
English Language Attitude (ELA)	.380**	.577	.040	.000	Reject H0
Situational Understanding Capacity (SUC)	.180**	.123	.044	.001	Reject H0
Moderator (ELA*MC)	.231**	.088	.056	.000	Reject H0
$R^2 = 0.679$	F-value = 127.118**			p-value = 0.000	

*Significant @ $p < 0.05$

This affirmed that situational understanding capability is an undeniable factor that help improved the interaction between English learning attitude and research interest of senior high school students. This supports Wanchid and Wattanasin (2015) concluded that situational understanding involves grasping the context in which language is used. By enhancing this capability, students can better appreciate the real-world applications of English. When students understand the relevance of English in various

situations, they may develop a more positive attitude towards learning the language, as they see it as a tool for communication and problem-solving. According to Toli and Kallery (2021), situational understanding often involves the ability to gather and process information effectively. This skill is essential for research. As students develop better situational understanding, they are likely to acquire improved research skills, allowing them to explore topics of interest more comprehensively and critically.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the conclusion and recommendation of the researcher. The discussion is supported by the literature presented in the first chapters and the conclusion is in accordance with statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to evaluate whether situational understanding capability moderate the interaction between English learning attitude and research interest of senior high school students utilizing non-experimental quantitative design using descriptive-correlation technique. The researcher selected the 202 senior high school students in Tugbok District in Davao City as the respondents through stratified random sampling method. The researcher made use of modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires which was pilot tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. English learning attitude of senior high school students got an overall mean of 3.48 with extensive descriptive rating. Also, English learning attitude of senior high school students in terms of behavior towards learning; understanding concepts; and feelings towards learning obtained the mean scores of 3.53, 3.50, and 3.42, respectively. Research interest of senior high school students has an overall mean of 3.31 with a moderately extensive descriptive rating. Also, research interest of senior high school students in terms of positive learning environment; technological proficiency; perceived competence; and reinforcement use obtained the mean scores 3.27, 3.44, 3.24, and 3.28, respectively. Moreover, situational understanding capability of senior high school students got a mean rating of 3.47 described as extensive. Partial Correlation Analysis indicated that English learning attitude has a significant positive relationship with the research interest of senior high school students when moderated by situational understanding capability with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .556$, $p < 0.05$). Situational understanding capability (SUC) is a significant moderator on the interaction between English learning attitude (ELA) and research interest (RI) of senior high school students. The analysis showed that when an

interaction between English learning attitude (ELA) and situational understanding capability (SUC) was added, the percentage of variance in research interest (RI) of senior high school students was 67.90

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study several conclusions were generated: English learning attitude of senior high school students was extensive. Meanwhile, English learning attitude of senior high school students in terms of behavior towards learning; understanding concepts; and feelings towards learning obtained extensive descriptive ratings. The result implies that students' beliefs, motivations, perceptions, and emotions related to studying and acquiring proficiency in English is oftentimes observed. Research interest of senior high school students was rated as moderately extensive. Research interest of senior high school students in terms of technological proficiency belong to extensive rating, while, research interest of senior high school students in terms of positive learning environment; perceived competence; and reinforcement obtained moderately extensive ratings. The result implies that the attraction or enthusiasm for activities, courses, or careers that involve the systematic and in-depth exploration, analysis, and research of various subjects, issues, or phenomena is sometimes manifested. Situational understanding capability of senior high school students was extensive. This means that students' ability to perceive, comprehend, and navigate various educational contexts, challenges, and situations effectively is oftentimes evident. There is significant positive relationship between English learning attitude has a significant positive relationship with the research interest of senior high school students when moderated by situational understanding capability. This shows that situational understanding requires critical thinking skills. Improving critical thinking can, in turn, enhance the ability to analyze and interpret information in both English learning and

research activities. Situational understanding capability is a significant moderator on the interaction between English learning attitude and research interest of senior high school students. It is emphasized in this study that situational understanding capability is an undeniable factor that intervened on the interaction between English learning attitude and research interest of senior high school students.

4.3. *Recommendations*—The Department of Education (DepEd) should review and update English language curriculum to include more real-world applications and research-oriented activities. DepEd should also invest in professional development opportunities for teachers to enhance their skills in integrating research and situational understanding in English language instruction. School heads should foster a school culture that values both English learning and research. Encourage teachers to experiment with innovative teaching methods. They should ensure that teachers have access to adequate resources, such as technology, research

materials, and professional development opportunities. Teachers should create opportunities for students to engage in research projects, encouraging them to explore topics of personal interest. Adding more, they should recognize and accommodate diverse learning styles, allowing students to approach English learning and research in ways that suit their strengths. Students should actively engage in English learning activities and seek out opportunities to apply language skills in real-life situations. They should also identify and explore personal research interests. Connect these interests to English learning, making the language more relevant and meaningful. Future researchers should conduct research on effective teaching methods that enhance English learning, research interest, and situational understanding. Adding more, they should advocate for policies that support innovative and effective approaches to English language education, including research-based learning.

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